

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AJAYI****FIRST NAME: OLUREMI****PROGRAM CODE : DILT****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student used Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 5%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office on Windows 7)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. The general rule on the use of punctuation in academic writing is to use punctuations as little as necessary, while retaining the meaning of the sentence. For example, an hyphen should be used in all of the following situations except:
 - In an adjectival phrase before a noun.
 - In an adjectival phrase including a verb participle.
 - In an adjectival phrase following a noun.**¹
 - With prefixes before inserting a proper name, number or date.
2. When preparing research questions, a researcher is aware that not all questions are viable to research and so they must explore research questions whose answers might

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University Publication, 2021), 21.

make readers think about the research topic in a new way. To this end, a researcher should therefore avoid researching questions that:

- Their answers are settled facts that any reader could just easily look up.
- Their answers would be merely speculative or even lead to dead ends.
- Their answers require more/different resources and/or even different capacities from the ones the researcher possesses.
- All of the above.**²

3. Plagiarism can be described as:

- Using information that is common knowledge or that can be found in numerous areas.**³
- Taking someone else's words or ideas without giving credit to the author.
- Having someone write a paper for you and then putting your name on it as though you are the original author.
- Quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from a borrowed source.

4. Although the choice of font may vary, a researcher can use any of the following different typefaces in legal writing or for law reviews except:

- Ordinary Roman (Plain Text).
- Underlined and Italicized.
- Large and Small Capitals.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 27-28.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 34-37.

Punctuations in United States English language.⁴

5. When a research involves numerical data, the general rule is that a researcher may subject to the research discipline, choose to spell out the numbers in words, use abbreviations for quantities, or make use of Arabic numerals. However, there are exceptions to this general rule, which does not include:

Numerical data from one through one hundred that is used only occasionally.⁵

Numbers beginning a sentence, especially when there are other numerals of a similar type in the sentence.

When it involves round numbers in isolation.

When there are a series of related numbers in the same sentence that are above and below the threshold.

6. In a qualitative research or dissertation, the key parts of the introduction chapter includes sub-topics like:

The research analysis.

The problem statement and statement of purpose of the research.⁶

The literature review.

⁴ Harvard Law Review Association, *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation* (Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard Law Review, 2010), 84-86.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 340-342.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End* (California: SAGE Publications Ltd, 2019), 74-75.

- The bibliography or reference page.
7. When citing a reference in a research paper, an author signals the source by placing a parenthetical citation that includes the author, date, and relevant page numbers next to the reference, only when using the:
- Note-bibliography style of citation.
- Author-date style of citation.**⁷
- Electronic or internet sources.
- Simple-notes citation style.
8. A style guide is an invaluable tool that a writer uses to document a research in alignment with the elements of a particular writing style or convention. A style guide is therefore valuable because:
- It ensures that a research is in an acceptable format and in alignment with the publication, company, or website associated with the writing.
- It ensures that a research publication does not carry the personal style of a writer.
- It ensures that the finished papers and publications are coherent and consistent.
- All of the above.**⁸

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 142.

⁸ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 40-42.

9. When using the Harvard Bluebook for legal citations or for citing sentences and clauses in law reviews, a researcher must take cognizance and align with the following introductory signals except:

- Signals that suggest a useful comparison.
- Signals that point directly to the research resource history.**⁹
- Signals that indicate background material.
- Signals that indicate contradiction.

10. A researcher engages in a research question, problem or topic that is researchable... and in determining whether or not a research question, problem or topic is researchable, it is key to ask pertinent questions like:

- Can the research problem be addressed by collecting and analyzing data?
- Is the time, resources, and skills to carry out the research available and is the research study (site and participants) accessible?
- Will the researcher be able to find an organization that will provide a written formal permission to conduct research at its site if needed?
- All of the above?**¹⁰

⁹ Harvard Law Review Association, *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*, 54-55.

¹⁰ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*, 310-311.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.